

antimicrobial activities of a series of Mannich bases of some 5-aryloxymethyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thiones (3a-c).

Compounds 3a-c were prepared by the reaction of appropriate aryloxyacetylhydrazides (2), prepared in turn from the aryloxyesters, and carbon disulphide in presence of ethanolic potassium hydroxide under reflux, followed by acidification³. The oxadiazoles (3) when treated with various substituted amines in presence of formaldehyde in alcohol medium gave moderate to good yields of the Mannich bases (4-6) (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1. Reagents : (i) Acetone + K₂CO₃, (ii) N₂H₄/EtOH, (iii) KOH/CS₂, (iv) EtOH, Δ, (v) HCHO + RNH₂/EtOH.

Synthesis and Biological Properties of Mannich Bases of some 5-Substituted-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thiones

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SOME Mannich bases of 5-substituted-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thione possess CNS depressant activity¹. The incorporation of aryloxymethyl substituent in various heterocycles enhances the biological activities². Prompted by these observations and in continuation of our work on the synthesis of nitrogen and sulphur containing heterocycles of biological interest, we report here the synthesis and

Biological studies : The Mannich bases (4-6) were screened *in vitro* for their antibacterial activity against gram-positive (*B. cirrflagels*) and Gram-negative (*E. coli*) bacteria employing the cup-plate method⁴ and for their fungitoxic properties against *A. niger* and *Candida albicans* at 10 μg concentration. The results revealed that 4b, 5a, 5b and 6a possess highest activity against *B. cirrflagels* while 5e and 6d possess higher activity against *E. coli*. Most of the Mannich bases showed excellent fungitoxic activity, comparable with that of the standard drug dapsone.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Pmr spectra (DMSO-d₆ or CDCl₃) were recorded on a Varian (60 MHz) or EM-390 (90 MHz) spectrometer and mass spectra on a Jeol JMS-D300 spectrometer at 70eV.

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NOTES

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 4–6*

Compd. no.	Ar	R	M.p. °C	Yield %
4a	1-Naphthyl	4-Chlorophenyl	180–83	68
4b	1-Naphthyl	2,4-Dichlorophenyl	82–84	72
4c	1-Naphthyl	Morpholine	118–20	65
5a	2-Naphthyl	4-Chlorophenyl	81–82	79
5b	2-Naphthyl	2,4-Dichlorophenyl	119–20	67
5c	2-Naphthyl	Morpholine	79–80	71
5d	2-Naphthyl	4-Carboxyphenyl	168–69	68
5e	2-Naphthyl	2-Methoxyphenyl	159–60	62
6a	3,5-Dimethylphenyl	4-Chlorophenyl	180–81	69
6b	3,5-Dimethylphenyl	2,4-Dichlorophenyl	104–5	82
6c	3,5-Dimethylphenyl	Morpholine	171–72	65
6d	3,5-Dimethylphenyl	4-Carboxyphenyl	80–81	69

* All compounds gave satisfactory C and H analyses.

5-Aryloxymethyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thione (3). *General procedure*: A mixture of aryloxyacetyl-drazide (0.1 mol), potassium hydroxide (5.6 g, 0.1 mol), carbon disulphide (20 ml) and ethanol (100 ml) was refluxed until the evolution of H₂S nearly stopped. The solvent was then removed under reduced pressure and the residue dissolved in water and acidified with dilute HCl. The resulting solid thiones (3) were recrystallised from ethanol: 3a (Ar=1-naphthyl) 68%, m.p. 135–36°; 3b (Ar=2-naphthyl) 72%, m.p. 89–90°; 3c (Ar=3,5-dimethylphenyl) 65%, m.p. 119–21°; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1 120 (C=S), 1 615 (C=N) and 3 340 cm⁻¹ (NH); δ (CDCl₃) 2.25 (6H, 2×CH₃), 4.65 (2H, s, OCH₂), 6.6–7.3 (3H, m, ArH) and 8.9 (1H, br, NH).

3-Arylaminomethyl-5-aryloxymethyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thione (4–6). *General procedure*: A solution of the appropriate thione (3; 0.01 mol), formaldehyde (40%; 1.5 ml) and the substituted amine (0.01 mol) in ethanol (20 ml) was stirred for 1 h and then left overnight at room temperature. The resulting solid was recrystallised from ethanol (Table 1): 6a *m/z* 375 (C₁₈H₁₈ClN₃O₂S), 236 and 122 (parent thione and phenol respectively); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1 080 (C=S), 1 640 (C=N) and 3 280 (NH); δ (DMSO-d₆) 2.15 (6H, s, 2×CH₃), 4.9 (2H, s, OCH₂), 5.5 (2H, s, NCH₂) and 6.9–7.8 (8H, m, ArH, NH).

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